

1 A METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH FOR THE EVALUATION OF
2 SOIL POLLUTION BY POTENTIALLY TOXIC TRACE ELEMENTS

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6
7 ABSTRACT

8 Risk assessment of soils polluted by potentially toxic trace elements
9 generally is a complex procedure that includes many variables and
10 parameters, many of them difficult to assess. The proposed methodological
11 approach is an easier procedure to obtain reasonable security for the
12 potential risk of a soil contaminated by trace elements. This approach can
13 be successfully applied in most of the study cases, avoiding a sometimes
14 flawed risk analysis procedure, which many times leads to an unnecessary
15 declaration of soil pollution, resulting in mandatory and expensive
16 reclamation actions.

17 The protocol supposes that: a) high concentrations of potentially toxic trace
18 elements exceeding generic reference levels are not always a risk to human
19 health, and b) the mobile fractions of potentially toxic trace elements and
20 their bioavailability are the key factors to consider in any sort of risk
21 assessment, when such assessments are needed.

22 The proposal consists of successive steps that ranges from a simple
23 documentation and investigation of available information of the history,
24 present state of the potential polluted site (PPS), mapping and field works
25 to a detailed study that involves determination of local reference values,
26 geoaccumulation factors, soil parameters, mobility, bioavailability,
27 operational speciation, etc. For As, Hg, Cd, and Pb, particular procedures
28 are also proposed.

29 As can be deduced from the proposal, anomalously high concentrations of
30 potentially toxic trace elements in a soil, although they may exceed the
31 generic reference levels, do not always pose a health risk. Thus, risk
32 assessment is only necessary in a very few cases.

33

34 KEY-WORDS: Soil pollution assessment; potentially toxic trace elements;
35 generic reference level; bioavailability; risk analysis.

36

37

38 INTRODUCTION

39 Soil is a dynamic system that is capable of trapping potentially toxic trace
40 elements (PTTEs) (including heavy metals and metalloids) avoiding their
41 passing to more sensitive media such as the hydrosphere and the biosphere.
42 Thus, soil acts a protective barrier by immobilizing and accumulating
43 PTTEs. The capacity for trapping them is dependent on the soil properties
44 and the physical and chemical environmental conditions. When a soil
45 reaches critical loading levels, it can be considered as polluted (for
46 example, Rieuwerts et al. 1998; Cheng et al. 2001; Salvagio et al 2002,
47 Nickolson et al 2003, de Vries et al. 2013). The assessment of soil pollution
48 is of paramount importance for the protection of soil ecological functions
49 and for agriculture (Wuana and Okieimen, 2011).

50 Trace elements can accumulate in soils by either geogenic or anthropogenic
51 processes. In fact, PTTEs loadings in soils usually reflect both geogenic
52 and anthropogenic contributions. The presence of geogenic trace elements
53 in soils is largely determined by their *geoavailability*, which is that portion
54 of the total content of a chemical element or a compound in an earth
55 material that can be liberated to the surficial or near-surface environment
56 through mechanical, chemical, or biological processes (Plumlee, 1994).
57 Geoavailable trace elements typically reach the soil when they are released
58 from their parent rock because of weathering. Together with metals derived
59 from volcanic emissions or from the leaching of ore minerals, they
60 constitute the so-called “geogenic metals”. Generally, the amount of
61 geoavailable trace elements released from the parent rocks into soil is
62 negligible compared to the amount having an anthropogenic origin. The
63 highest levels of trace elements in soils that are inherited from the parent
64 rock are typically those of Cr, Mn and Ni, followed by Co, Cu, Zn and Pb;
65 moreover, As, Cd and Hg are usually present at very low concentrations.
66 Nevertheless, in some cases the geogenic contributions in soils can be as
67 high as 20% of the total (Ludden et al. 2015).

69 Anthropogenic trace elements enter the soil via several pathways and
70 activities, including aerial deposition, acid mine drainage, smelting
71 operations, fertilizer and pesticide applications, sewage sludge amendment,
72 dredged sediment disposal, irrigation water and some urban activities
73 (González et al. 2011; Wuana and Okieimen, 2011). One of the principal
74 source of soil contamination is mining activity, which is considered as a
75 problem of global dimensions around the world (for example, Davies and
76 Ballinger, 1990; Lin et al., 2005; Aleksander-Kwaterczak and Hellios-
77 Rybicka, 2009; González et al., 2011; Madejón et al., 2011; Carvalho et al.,
78 2012; Kossoff et al. 2012; Abreu et al., 2014b; Perez Sirvent et al 2014,
79 Romero et al., 2018).

80 The distinction among geogenic and anthropogenic trace elements in a soil
81 is of paramount importance for determining whether a soil is polluted
82 (Galán et al., 2014a; Petrik et al., 2018). Firstly, only the anthropogenic
83 contributions are of primary concern in soil pollution, because they are the
84 only ones that are legally considered as true contaminants. On the other
85 hand, geogenic elements usually are below threshold values (González et
86 al. 2011) and, even if these levels are exceeded, they usually show a low
87 availability, which reduce the risk for toxicity (Romero et al., 2012; Galán
88 et al., 2014a; Romero et al., 2018).

89 Distinguishing the contribution of geogenic and anthropogenic sources is
90 not always easy to achieve, particularly in mining areas. A good and
91 practical methodological approach for estimating the geogenic contribution
92 in a soil potentially polluted by PTTEs was recently proposed by Galán et
93 al. (2014a). That paper also discusses the limitations of other “classical”
94 approaches proposed for the estimation of the anthropogenic input versus
95 the background, namely the contamination factor (CF), the enrichment
96 factor (EF) and the geoaccumulation index (Igeo).

97 PTTEs can be mobilized by physical, chemical and biological vectors, and
98 they can leave soils by volatilization, dissolution, leaching or erosion.
99 When PTTEs are in a bioavailable (i.e., relatively soluble) form, they can
100 enter organisms (Adriano, 2001; Kabata-Pendias, 2004, 2011). Thus, the
101 contamination by trace elements represents one of the most prominent
102 environmental potential hazards to health, and the assessment of soil

103 pollution is one of the most important environmental issues.

104 Presently, most procedures for assessing soil pollution due to trace
105 elements are based on chemical analysis. When the total content of a PTTE
106 in a soil exceeds the Generic Reference Level (GRL) (usually referred as
107 screening level), i.e. the element concentration in soil below which no
108 hazard may be expected, the soil is considered as potentially polluted and a
109 risk analysis is mandatory (US-EPA, 2001; Carlon 2007).

110 However, the total content is not a significant value from a toxicological
111 point of view (Singh, 1997; de Groot et al., 1998), because trace elements
112 in soils interact with other components and thereby change their activity,
113 mobility and their derivative effects (Baker et al., 2003; Adriano et al.,
114 2004). Even the “total” or pseudototal contents of trace elements in soils,
115 (those measured on *aqua regia* solutions) (Tarvainen and Kallio, 2002;
116 Albanese et al. 2007), which are used by the EU as indicators for
117 environmental policies, do not represent accurate information about the
118 available fractions of those elements. Instead, they often represent the
119 worst possible situation and overestimate the real risk.

120 In addition, each state or region calculates its own GRL using different
121 approaches, which result in very different values. Thus, this reference
122 should be just one aspect that should be considered in a more general
123 assessment.

124 On the other hand, classic “risk analyses” do not perform well in assessing
125 pollution by trace elements, due to the geogenic contribution (Galán et al.,
126 2014a), and the most frequently applied programs may enter unwarranted
127 results (Galán et al., 2014b; Rivera et al., 2016).

128 Actually, the official regulations based on the criteria listed above are not
129 very accurate for soil polluted by trace elements, because the criteria are
130 not very scientifically sound. Therefore, a new approach for the
131 management of soil polluted by PTTEs is proposed. A good methodology
132 should take into account the mobility of the trace elements in the soil and
133 the bioavailable fraction, which is the most potentially toxic fraction
134 (Lanno et al., 1999), as well as information on the elements’ operational
135 and mineralogical speciation. Those data are also of utmost importance to
136 predict the remaining health risk after remediation actions.

137 The proposal described in this paper summarizes a protocol which has as
138 its objective the creation of a decision tool for use by environmental
139 administration, enterprises and private owners to determine whether a soil
140 represents an unacceptable health risk because of its content of PTTEs
141 (particularly As, Cd, Cr, Co, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb and Zn). The results of the
142 application of this protocol to a potentially polluted site may be used to
143 declare whether the site is polluted and whether it needs reclamation
144 actions, if so.

145 The proposal is based on the following criteria: the mobility, availability,
146 bioavailability and speciation of the trace elements; the soil parameters
147 controlling the trace element mobility; the assessed origin of the elements
148 in the soil (geogenic *vs.* anthropogenic origin); the regional and local
149 geochemical baselines of the site where the soil occurs; and the generic
150 reference levels.

151 The proposed protocol supposes that a) high concentrations of toxic trace
152 elements exceeding GRL are not always a risk to human health, and b) the
153 mobile fractions of toxic trace elements contained in a soil and their
154 bioavailability are the key factors to consider in any sort of risk assessment,
155 when such assessments are needed.

156 To permit better understanding of the protocol and its application, the
157 concepts discussed above will be developed briefly.

158

159 BASIC ISSUES AND TERMINOLOGY USED IN THE PROTOCOL

160 Trace elements are present at low concentrations (mg.kg^{-1}) in the earth's
161 crust, soils and plants. Many of them are essential for plant, animal and
162 human growth but can be toxic above certain concentration levels, which
163 differ from one element to another (Siegel, 2002). Occasionally, soil is
164 polluted with high concentrations of major elements such as Na, Fe or Al.

165 From all of the trace elements found in soil, the latest US Environmental
166 Protection Agency (EPA) list of priority pollutants includes the following
167 13 trace elements: Ag, As, Be, Cd, Cr, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb, Sb, Se, Tl and Zn.
168 Among these elements, the most common in polluted soils are As, Cd, Cr,
169 Cu, Hg, Pb, and Zn. However, Co and Ni are also very abundant in some

170 types of soils; in spite of their lower toxicity, the protocol proposed will be
171 focused on those nine elements. The Agency for Toxic Substances and
172 Disease Registry (ATSDR) has determined the minimal risk level of these
173 elements; their more significant health toxic effects are summarized in
174 Table 1.

175 By definition, a pollutant is a contaminant, but not all contaminants are
176 pollutants (Chapman, 2007). A pollutant in a soil must always be found in
177 anomalous (higher than usual) concentrations and must have a harmful
178 impact on some organisms. Thus, an element (whether it is a contaminant
179 or not) must pass from the soil into the solution. That is, the element should
180 be available and the danger it poses will depend on its “availability”. The
181 more specific term *bioavailability* is the degree to which a contaminant in a
182 potential source is available for uptake (that is, movement into or onto an
183 organism) (Newman and Jagoe, 1994).

184 An easy method to define the soil concentration of trace elements available
185 for uptake by biota was applied to soils in Finland by Tarvainen and Kallio
186 (2002). This method consisted of the determination of “total” (hot *aqua*
187 *regia* extraction) and “bioavailable” (acetic acid, ammonium acetate and
188 EDTA extraction) trace element concentrations. In such cases, the
189 “bioavailable” concentrations were only 1-5% of the “total” concentrations.

190 There are a lot of methods for assessing the mobility and availability of
191 PTTEs, such as calcium chloride, calcium nitrate, ammonium nitrate or
192 ammonium acetate (Kabata-Pendias, 2004; Anjos et al., 2012; Abreu et al.,
193 2012, 2014a, Pinto et al., 2015). Other simple methods commonly used are
194 extraction with neutral or slightly acidic water and extractions with DTPA
195 or 0.05 M EDTA at pH 7, which are particularly effective for assessing the
196 transferability of divalent cations to plants (Quevauvilier et al., 1998;
197 Kabata-Pendias, 2004; Abreu 2014b; Anjos et al., 2012; Monterroso et al.,
198 2014; Pinto et al., 2015). These methods can only be used to discriminate
199 between residual metals and metals extracted by water or a mild organic
200 solvent.

201 The distribution coefficient between soil and water governs the
202 bioavailability of trace elements to organisms contacting the soil. Weakly
203 bound elements are highly bioavailable, and strongly bound elements are
204 less bioavailable. Therefore, the application of these methods may yield

205 information on the short-term risk posed by some elements. However, the
206 value of this coefficient depends upon both the properties of the element
207 species and the components of the soil.

208 Soil parameters influence the mobility of trace elements and the sensitivity
209 to contaminant influx. Factors that contribute to the mobility and
210 availability of trace elements and their ability to pass to other ecosystems
211 include pH (Evans et al., 1995), texture, cation exchange capacity, redox
212 potential (Chuang et al., 1996), and salinity (Du Laing et al., 2009), as well
213 as the abundances of carbonates (Martínez and Motto, 2000), clay minerals
214 (Bradl, 2004), organic matter (Guo et al., 2006), and Fe and Mn oxides and
215 hydroxides (Covelo et al., 2007). In general, the strongest adsorption of
216 PTTEs occurs, excluding oxy-anions, in those soils with higher pH, cation
217 exchange capacity, and abundances of organic matter and clay minerals
218 (Sposito, 1989; Galán, 2000; González et al. 2011).

219 To provide a rough estimation of the distribution of trace elements in the
220 different soil phases and their relative mobility, a more complex extraction
221 method can be used, specifically *sequential chemical extractions*. Such
222 methods use different specific extractants that are based on complex
223 reactions. The result is an operational speciation that leads to the
224 partitioning of the elements into the main soil phases and their relative
225 mobility (Tessier et al., 1979; Ure et al. 1993).

226 For mining soils, specific sequential extraction procedures combined with
227 differential X-ray diffraction (DXRD) have been proposed to detect which
228 minerals are dissolving in each leach (Dold, 2003). This procedure is more
229 robust because it combines information about chemical speciation with
230 information about mineralogical speciation. However, in some polluted
231 soils, trace elements are usually associated with minor phases that are
232 difficult to detect by X-ray diffraction (XRD). Other techniques, such as
233 scanning electron microscopy combined with energy dispersive X-ray
234 spectroscopy (SEM-EDS), can be coupled to sequential extractions and can
235 be used to determine mineralogical speciation (González et al., 2011).

236 However, the plant-available fraction of an element in soil also depends on
237 its *chemical speciation*, i.e., its oxidation state, and its *functional*
238 *speciation*, which distinguishes between different molecular forms. As
239 shown in Table 1, for some PTTEs, such as As, Cr, and Hg, it is also

240 convenient to determine the chemical and/or functional speciation. The
241 analytical techniques for determining the chemical speciation of these
242 elements are summarized in Table 2 (Galán et al., 2012).

243 Although claiming that a soil is polluted is purely an administrative action,
244 to demonstrate pollution is not an easy task. Contamination could also be
245 defined as the presence of an anomalously high level of a given element in
246 the soil. However, since no soil in the world is pristine and completely
247 uncontaminated, it is quite difficult to determine if soils have been directly
248 contaminated or not.

249 The term *contamination threshold* usually defines the concentration
250 (mg/kg) of trace elements in soil above which certain actions are
251 recommended or enforced (Carlson, 2007). They represent the highest levels
252 allowed in unpolluted soils. In any case, thresholds must always be checked
253 against toxicological tests before they are deemed accurate. Additionally,
254 any soil with element levels exceeding their respective thresholds is not
255 necessarily polluted, even if it contains trace elements at concentrations
256 over their regional means. Only a properly conducted toxicological study
257 can determine the exact allowable bioavailable amount of a trace element
258 and its toxicity.

259 A first step in evaluating the pollution content of a soil is to compare its
260 concentrations of PTTEs with background values. The *geochemical*
261 *background* of a chemical element represents its concentration in
262 uncontaminated soil. However, because it is virtually impossible to
263 determine, it is usually replaced by the *geochemical baseline*, which is the
264 average of superficial geochemical variations of the concentration at the
265 time of sampling (Salminen and Tarvainen, 2001; Baize and Sterckeman,
266 2001; Tarvainen and Kallio, 2002). It is influenced by subsoil lithology and
267 the presence of diffuse anthropic contamination. Thus, it is the sum of the
268 background value and the effect of diffuse anthropogenic contamination.

269 A more accurate baseline is the *regional geochemical baseline*, or the
270 geochemical background level for each region and element, as determined
271 for the specific geological context of the region (de Vivo et al., 1998; Galán
272 et al., 2008). These values allow us to discriminate between natural and
273 anthropogenic contamination. Additionally, they allow the potential
274 allowable load of an element in a specific soil to be determined from

275 contextual variables such as geology, history and use, thus providing the
276 competent authorities with reference levels.

277 Reference values (RVs) are usually determined for the same geotectonic
278 unit as the median or mean of uncontaminated soils or by other statistical
279 methods. RV shows the concentration above which the soil loses
280 performance. It is the security threshold.

281 Sometimes it is also necessary to determine *the local baseline*, i.e., the
282 baseline of the area where the potential polluted site (or soil) (PPS) is
283 included because the anomalous values recorded at particular sites could be
284 geogenic, and because the local baseline is more representative than the
285 geochemical baseline (Galán et al. 2014a).

286 In any case, human health can only be protected by setting the so-called
287 *generic reference levels* (GRLs), which allow us to efficiently manage
288 contaminated soils. According to the US-EPA (2001), the GRL of a
289 particular element indicates the element concentration in soil below which
290 no hazards may be expected, and the risk threshold that determines whether
291 human health can be affected. When GRL is exceeded at a specific site, the
292 soil should be carefully analysed in order to assess potential risks from
293 contamination. The GRLs are established in terms of two main criteria:
294 guiding the assessment and controlling contaminated soils (*viz.* land use
295 and human health hazards). This provides a crucial means to investigate
296 and manage them. GRLs for selected elements and countries are recorded
297 in Table 3.

298 As a rule, the GRL for an element is the lowest concentration that generates
299 an impact via the most sensitive pathway(s) (US-EPA-2001). However,
300 high concentrations of PTTEs exceeding generic reference levels are not
301 always a risk to human health. The mobile fraction of PTTEs in soils and
302 their bioavailability are the factors that should be considered in any sort of
303 risk assessment.

304 Risk analysis applied to soil consists of a set of studies which analyse the
305 risks posed by a potentially polluted soil to human health and ecosystems,
306 based on a conceptual model. Computer programs used for risk analysis are
307 based on probabilistic methods derived from conceptual models. They are
308 applied to soils when GRLs are exceeded. The risk is defined on the basis

309 of the probability of negative events produced by exposure to a polluted
310 soil.

311 Some qualitative models include the RBCA-Toolkit (EEUU), Risk Human
312 (The Netherlands), and CLEA (UK), with RBCA being the most used
313 (Baciocchia et al., 2010; Barsby et al., 2012; Fernández-Caliani, 2012;
314 Gabary and Fernández-Caliani, 2017).

315 The RBCA Tool Kit for Chemical Releases is based on the Risk Based
316 Corrective Action (RBCA) methodology developed by the American
317 Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) (Connor and McHugh, 2002;
318 Connor et al., 2007). Although it is a tool that is frequently used to make
319 decisions, such as the identification of polluted soil and the need for
320 cleaning actions, sealing, etc., its direct application to the study of soils
321 contaminated by trace elements can sometimes lead to needlessly alarming
322 and unreasonable results.

323 In performing a risk analysis with the RBCA Tool Kit, there are a number
324 of well-differentiated stages, including defining exposure pathways (direct
325 ingestion, dermal contact, inhalation or vegetable ingestion) and choosing
326 transport models; air, soil and groundwater parameters; toxicological
327 parameters; etc. The calculated baseline risk values and cleanup level
328 values can be viewed either according to individual pathways, or as a
329 summary of all the pathways. In the same way, these values are shown for
330 individual elements and cumulative risk is shown for multiple elements.

331 When the baseline risks are being calculated, the program allows the user
332 to modify the exposure parameters (time or frequency of exposure,
333 ingestion rate, etc.) according to the types of receptors. Toxicological
334 parameters can be selected according to databases used in the USA, the
335 Netherlands or the UK, or they can be modified and supplemented by the
336 user as necessary or desired. These values must be considered, since the
337 use of different databases generates results that may differ by up to two
338 orders of magnitude (Galán et al., 2014b). Other chemical parameters such
339 as availability or biotransfer factors are included in the database, but they
340 may be very different from the real ones.

341 This type of methodology is increasingly being used in different studies
342 (i.e., Banwart and Malmstrom, 2001; Avagliano et al., 2005; Baciocchi et

343 al., 2010; Galán et al., 2014b; García de Lorenzo et al 2014; Rivera et al.,
344 2016; Gabari and Fernández-Caliani, 2014). However, it should be used
345 with caution, so as not to obtain absurd results. Important factors, such as
346 bioavailability, biotransference and leaching, should be calculated instead
347 of using the values preset by the program (Rivera et al., 2016). Another
348 option is to use direct values of elements in water or fruit rather than using
349 transport models or transfer factors (Avagliano et al., 2005; Madeira et al.,
350 2012). In any case, it is recommended to check the results obtained to
351 verify that they are possible and reasonable.

352

353 THE PROTOCOL FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF SOILS POLLUTED 354 BY POTENTIALLY TOXIC TRACE ELEMENTS.

355 The new approach for the evaluation of soils potentially polluted by trace
356 elements consists of a series of successive stages that ranges from a simple
357 documentation and investigation of available information on the history,
358 present state of the PPS, mapping and field works to detailed study that
359 involves the determination of local reference values, enrichment and
360 geoaccumulation factors, soil parameters, mobility, bioavailability,
361 operational speciation, etc.

362 The stages of the procedure must be followed step by step. The procedure
363 can be stopped at any time when the research carried out up to that point
364 suggests that the soil is unpolluted, or that it is potentially polluted but
365 poses no actual risk. For each step, some hypotheses must be formulated,
366 based on the criteria and considerations cited and discussed above.
367 According to the results obtained at each stage, the hypotheses can be
368 checked and the passage to the following stage will depend on the
369 assessment of the new data.

370 The philosophy that underlies the application of this protocol is not to
371 declare a soil as polluted until the soil shows an unacceptable health risk,
372 which should be determined using different and independent criteria.

373 The proposal is illustrated by the flow-sheet shown in Figure 1. It consists
374 of three stages. The first one is a Preliminary Investigation of the PPS
375 (Stage 1). In this stage, all the documentation available, including mapping,
376 land use, soil data, etc., is examined. Moreover, a field survey of the site is

377 conducted to check the mapping, identify probable pollutant sources, and
378 characterize the spatial distribution of the contamination, its heterogeneity
379 and other factors. This information leads to the formulation of a hypothesis:
380 is there a sufficient basis for considering the site to be polluted? If there are
381 no conclusive data, the soil is potentially unpolluted, and only some test
382 samples are advisable. In contrast, if the diagnostic obtained from this
383 preliminary investigation is positive, or test samples are positive, we would
384 need to perform a Preliminary Sampling of the site, including chemical
385 analysis of the trace elements and determination of the main soil
386 parameters influencing the elements' mobility (pH, carbonate and organic
387 matter content, clay mineralogy, etc.).

388 With all these results in hand, it is possible to assess the magnitude of the
389 problem, including the area affected, the sources of the pollution, and the
390 severity of the problem. If this assessment points toward a need for an in-
391 depth investigation, the next step will be a Detailed Investigation (Stage 2).
392 To carry out this stage, both detailed sampling of the polluted site and a
393 complementary sampling program to determine the local baseline are
394 necessary.

395 The sampling strategy should take into account the heterogeneity and size
396 of the site, the contaminant type, the accuracy in the evaluation of
397 pollution, the analytical techniques available for the analysis, etc. Thus, the
398 sampling must be planned carefully, and it must be representative in any
399 case. In the calculation of the local baseline, the sampling of potentially
400 contaminated soils should be avoided, and samples must be collected on
401 soils with the same parent lithologies as those represented within the
402 polluted site.

403 The data on the area surrounding the PPS represent the geochemical
404 anomalies of the natural setting where the PPS is located, and they are of
405 interest because the local baseline is more representative than the
406 geochemical regional baseline, and also because the entire area, including
407 the site, could be a geogenic anomaly (Galán et al., 2014a).

408 The following analyses should be carried out on the samples collected from
409 the PPS: chemical analysis of the PTTEs, soil parameters, mobility,
410 bioavailability and operational speciation. Chemical results must be
411 compared with the threshold value (TV) of those elements in the

412 corresponding unit and with the local baselines. If the content of a PTTEs
413 in the soil is higher than TV and higher than the local threshold level
414 (LTV), an anthropogenic input exists, which will also be reflected by a
415 high enrichment factor. At the same time, if this value is greater than the
416 corresponding generic reference level, then the site is potentially polluted
417 with respect to this element. In addition, if the element shows large
418 mobility and bioavailability and is bound to labile soil fractions, the soil (or
419 the entire site, if the anomaly is extensively distributed within the
420 investigated area) is actually polluted. However, on the contrary, if the
421 mobility is low and the element is bound to the soil residual fraction, the
422 soil is potentially polluted, because the PTTEs is immobile under present
423 environmental conditions.

424 The assessment of the results of detailed investigation will lead to a
425 conclusion as to whether or not a real hazard exists. For soils that are
426 potentially polluted, monitoring and supervision over time is advisable,
427 including periodic checking. However, when a real hazard exists and the
428 soil is (or will be) dedicated to “sensible uses” (agriculture, gardens, cattle,
429 etc.) a risk analysis and assessment is required. Based on this analysis, the
430 soil will be finally considered as polluted and remediation actions should
431 be carried out (Stage 3). Otherwise, it will be considered potentially
432 polluted; in that case, strict checking over time is needed.

433 This is the general flow-sheet to follow for most of the PTTEs, but for
434 those elements whose toxicity depends on their oxidation state (i.e., Hg, Cr,
435 As, Pb), data on chemical speciation and the determination of the mobile
436 fraction of the more dangerous oxidation state can be essential.

437 Therefore, during the Detailed Investigation (Stage 2), some precautions
438 should be taken when the main PTTE is Pb, Cr, As or Hg. Specific
439 protocols should be proposed when the total content in the soil achieves the
440 following values:

441 Cr > p90 Regional Geochemical Baseline, or Cr > Local Geochemical
442 Baseline

443 As > p90 Regional Geochemical Baseline, or As > Local Geochemical
444 Baseline

445 Hg > Maximum regional value, or Hg > Local Geochemical Baseline

446 In the case of Pb, the main soil parameters controlling its sorption and
447 mobility are pH, Eh, and the abundance of Fe and Mn oxy-hydroxides,
448 organic matter, carbonates and chlorides (Adriano, 2001). In such cases,
449 Stage 2 must be modified, paying particular attention to the relevant
450 geoedaphic parameters (Figure 2). In addition, in selected samples
451 assessing mobility using different extracting agents (water at pH 5 and 7;
452 EDTA or DTPA) is advisable, as well as sequential extraction according to
453 the BCR method (Ure et al. 1993) for agricultural soils or according to the
454 Dold (2003) method for mining soils. In addition, because Pb intake by
455 human is mostly through particle inhalation, a SEM+EDS study is
456 advisable to know the particle-size of the Pb compounds to assess the
457 possible human risk by inhalation. The risk will be higher for particles
458 below 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) (WHO, 2005).

459 Assessment of the results leads to the conclusion that the soil is potentially
460 polluted when Pb is immobile, when the mobile fraction is less than (or
461 equal) to its GRL, or when it is less than (or equal) to the mobile fraction in
462 the local unpolluted area, and when the average particle size of the Pb-
463 compounds is > PM_{2.5}. In contrast, when the average particle size of Pb-
464 compounds is <PM_{2.5}, there is a real hazard. In the same way, there will be a
465 real hazard if Pb is mobile or its mobile fraction is greater than the GRL or
466 greater than the mobile fraction in the local unpolluted area. In this last
467 case, given that the toxic behaviour of Pb is very different if it occurs as
468 inorganic Pb or as an organic compound, data on chemical speciation are
469 necessary.

470 For Cr, the issue is somewhat different. Cr(III) is not toxic, has very limited
471 mobility, and is mainly controlled by organic matter in the soil. However,
472 Cr(VI) is very mobile and bioavailable. In addition, the conversion from
473 Cr(III) to Cr(VI) depends on redox potential. Thus, Eh and the content of
474 organic matter in the soil are parameters of paramount importance for Cr.
475 Its mobility in water should be measured at pH 5 and 9, because Cr(VI) is
476 highly mobile under alkaline pH conditions (Richard and Bourg, 1991;
477 Fendorf, 1995). The determination of bioavailability using EDTA and
478 sequential extraction using the BCR method will help to characterize the
479 scenario (Figure 3).

480 A similar reasoning as that used for Pb may be done if there is a significant
481 mobile fraction of Cr and data on chemical speciation is advisable. The site
482 should be considered to be potentially polluted if the total Cr is less than
483 (or equal) to the GRL for Cr(VI) or less than the mobile Cr in the local
484 area. Otherwise, there is a real hazard.

485 Arsenic is a very toxic element, and it is very common (and sometimes
486 abundant) in soils. Its mobility is mainly controlled by “amorphous” and
487 crystalline Fe and Mn oxy-hydroxides (absorbents), and pH and Eh
488 variations are also very important. As(III) is ten times more toxic than
489 As(V), and in a soil with As anomalies, both must be assessed (using
490 chemical speciation) because their activities (mobility and toxicity) are
491 very different (Bissen and Frimmel, 2003; Kabata-Pendias, 2011)). As
492 shown in Figure 4, the measurement of pH, Eh, and Fe and Mn oxy-
493 hydroxides in the soil; mobility in water at pH 5, 7 and 9; and
494 bioavailability using EDTA, as well as sequential extraction and
495 mineralogical speciation data, are necessary. Then, a similar assessment of
496 the results, as in the case of Cr, may be done to conclude if a real hazard
497 exists in the soil, and a risk analysis can be performed based on the use of
498 the soil (Figure 4).

499 The oxidation states of mercury are Hg^0 , Hg^{2+} and Hg_2^{2+} . The first is volatile
500 at room temperature. This metal in soils can be free, adsorbed, chelated, or
501 in mineral forms (i.e., as carbonate, hydroxide, or sulfide phases).
502 However, in the presence of dissolved organic matter (DOM) or salts, Hg
503 can form complexes. Its mobility and bioavailability depend on oxidation
504 state, which is controlled by pH, Eh, DOM and salinity (Schuster, 1991;
505 Finzgar et al., 2007; Kushwaha et al., 2018), and these are significant
506 parameters to be examined in the soil. Hg bioavailability is low in general
507 and decreases in soils containing DOM and sulphur (Figure 5)

508 Consequently, in detailed investigations of soils with high Hg anomalies,
509 the cited soil parameters must be determined. It is advisable to assess
510 bioavailability with EDTA and $CaCl_2$. For the sequential extraction, it is
511 advisable to use the method indicated in Table 2, as well as to determine
512 the total Hg^0 concentration.

513 For this metal, a real hazard exists when the mobile Hg fraction is greater

514 than the GRL, greater than local area's mobile Hg, or when Hg⁰ is greater
515 than the Hg GRL. Surprisingly little attention is paid to this dangerous
516 metal (Fig. 5).

517 CONCLUSIONS

518 The proposed method is a) easy to apply, b) gives reasonable assessments
519 of the potential risk posed by soil contaminated by potentially toxic trace
520 elements, c) can be successfully applied to almost any kind of case study,
521 c) avoids a risk analysis procedure that may lead to a declaration that a soil
522 is polluted and to expensive remediation actions that are not really needed,
523 and d) saves time and money for administrators, enterprises and private
524 owners relative to "classical" assessments based on risk analysis.

525 As can be deduced from the proposal, anomalously high concentrations of
526 potentially toxic elements in a soil, although they may exceed the generic
527 reference levels, do not always pose a health risk. The mobile fraction of
528 the trace elements in a potentially polluted soil and their bioavailability are
529 the key factors to consider in a polluted soil. Thus, risk assessment is only
530 necessary in a very few cases.

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815

816 TABLES AND FIGURES CAPTIONS

817 **Table 1** Toxicological parameters and carcinogenic classification of the
818 most common elements found in polluted soils. (In terms of duration, acute
819 = 1 to 14 days, intermediate = 15 to 364 days, and chronic = 1 year or
820 longer). IARC (1997); ATSDR (2016)

821

822 **Table 2** Analytical techniques recommended for determining the chemical
823 speciation of As, Cr, Hg and Pb (Modified from Galán et al., 2012)

824

825 **Table 3** Generic reference levels for different elements and countries

826

827 **Fig. 1** Flow-sheet diagram for the management of potentially polluted soils,
828 including the study stages

829

830 **Fig. 2** Flow-sheet diagram for the management of sites potentially polluted
831 by lead

832

833 **Fig. 3** Flow-sheet diagram for the management of sites potentially polluted
834 by chromium

835

836 **Fig. 4** Flow-sheet diagram for the management of sites potentially polluted
837 by arsenic

838

839 **Fig. 5** Flow-sheet diagram for the management of sites potentially polluted
840 by mercury

MANAGEMENT OF POTENTIALLY POLLUTED SOIL

SITE POTENTIALLY POLLUTED BY LEAD

SITE POTENTIALLY POLLUTED BY CHROMIUM

SITE POTENTIALLY POLLUTED BY ARSENIC

DETAILED INVESTIGATION (Phase 2)

SITE DATA
As > p90 Regional Geochemical baseline
As > Local threshold

ASSESSMENT OF ANOMALIES

- Comparison with baseline and generic reference level (GRL)
- Geoaccumulation and enrichment factors
- Mapping of anomalies

DETERMINATION OF GEOEDAPHIC PARAMETERS

- pH, Eh
- Texture
- Fe and Mn oxyhydroxides
- Organic matter
- Carbonates
- Mineralogy

Mobility and Bioavailability
(Selected samples)

- Mobility in water (pH 5, pH 7, pH 9)
- Bioavailability (EDTA)
- Sequential extraction (Dold method), and mineralogical speciation

ASSESSMENT OF RESULTS

POTENTIAL POLLUTION
Immobile As
PPS mobile As ≤ GRL
PPS mobile As ≤ natural area mobile As

REAL HAZARD
Mobile As
PPS mobile As > GRL, or
PPS mobile As > natural area mobile As

Chemical speciation of As

Insensitive use of soil

ASSESSMENT OF RESULTS IN RELATION TO SOIL USE

Highly sensitive use of soil

NO

Risk Analysis necessary?

YES

RISK ANALYSIS using computer programs

MONITORING, SUPERVISION AND CONTROL (PPS)

POLLUTED SOIL DECLARATION

REMEDIACTION ACTIONS

SITE POTENTIALLY POLLUTED BY MERCURY

Table 1 Toxicological parameters and carcinogenic classification of the most common elements found in polluted soils. (In terms of duration, acute = 1 to 14 days, intermediate = 15 to 364 days, and chronic = 1 year or longer). IARC (1997); ATSDR (2016).

Element	Minimal risk level (MRL) according to ATSDR (2016)			IARC Classification
	Route	Duration	MRL	
As	Oral	Acute	0.005 mg/kg/day	Arsenic and arsenic compounds are carcinogenic to humans (Group I). The level of toxicity is Arsine > As(III) inorganic > As(III) organic > As(V) inorganic > As(V) organic > elemental As
	Oral	Chronic	0.0003 mg/kg/day	
Cd	Inhalation	Acute	0.00003 mg/m ³	Cadmium and cadmium compounds are carcinogenic to humans (Group I)
	Inhalation	Chronic	0.00001 mg/m ³	
	Oral	Intermediate	0.0005 mg/kg/day	
	Oral	Chronic	0.0001 mg/kg/day	
Co	Inhalation	Chronic	0.0001 mg/m ³	Cobalt and cobalt compounds are possibly carcinogenic to humans (Group IIB)
	Oral	Intermediate	0.01 mg/kg/day	
	Radiactive	Acute	4 mSv	
	Radiactive	Chronic	1 mSv/yr	
Cr	Chromium (III) isolate particulates	Oral	Acute	Metallic chromium and chromium[III] compounds are not classifiable as to their carcinogenicity to humans (Group 3)
	Chromium (III) soluble particulates	Inhalation	Intermediate	
		Inhalation	Intermediate	
Cr	Chromium (VI)	Oral	Intermediate	Chromium (VI) compounds are carcinogenic to humans (Group I)
		Oral	Chronic	
	Chromium (VI) aerosol	Inhalation	Intermediate	
		Inhalation	Chronic	

	Chromium (VI) particulates	Inhalation	Intermediate	0.0003 mg/m3	
Cu		Oral	Acute	0.01 mg/kg/day	Copper compounds are not classifiable as to their carcinogenicity to humans (Group III).
		Oral	Intermediate	0.01 mg/kg/day	
	Inorganic	Inhalation	Chronic	0.0002 mg/m3	Methylmercury compounds are possibly carcinogenic to humans (Group IIB).
Hg	Methylmercury	Oral	Chronic	0.0003 mg/kg/day	Metallic mercury and inorganic mercury compounds are not classifiable as to their carcinogenicity to humans (Group III).
Ni		Inhalation	Intermediate	0.0002 mg/m3	Niquel metallic is a possibly carcinogenic to humans (Group IIB)
		Inhalation	Chronic	0.00009 mg/m3	
Pb	MRLs were not derived for lead because a clear threshold for some of the more sensitive effects in humans has not been identified.				Inorganic lead compounds are probably carcinogenic to humans (Group IIA) Organic lead compounds are not classifiable as to their carcinogenicity to humans (Group III).
Zn		Oral	Intermediate	0.3 mg/kg/day	Zinc compounds are not classifiable as to their carcinogenicity to humans (Group III).
		Oral	Chronic	0.3 mg/kg/day	

Table 2 Analytical techniques recommended for determining the chemical speciation of As, Cr, Hg and Pb (Modified from Galán et al., 2012)

Element	Species	Analytical method
As	As (III) As (V)	Extraction solid-liquid with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and measurement by high pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC) coupled to inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)
Cr	Cr (III) Cr (VI)	Pre-formation of the Cr (III)-AEDT complex and subsequent separation of Cr (VI) by ICP-MS coupled ion chromatography.
Hg	Hg ⁰ Hg (II) Monomethylmercury MMHg ⁺ Dimethylmercury-DMHg Diethylmercury- DEHg	For the analysis of elemental mercury (Hg ⁰) (volatile) thermosorption in a quartz furnace under a nitrogen stream and analysis of the mercury vapor by atomic fluorescence are recommended. Organic mercury species and inorganic mercury (Hg ²⁺) can be determined by HPLC-ICP-MS or a coupled gas chromatography system with AFS detector.
Pb	R ₄ Pb, R ₃ Pb ⁺ , R ₂ Pb ²⁺	Gas chromatography - mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis with subsequent detection by atomic absorbance spectroscopy (GC-AAS). In a previous step, derivatization of the polar species of lead is carried out by alkylation using the Grignard reaction or ethylation in an aqueous medium with sodium tetraethyl borate. In addition to this technique, it is also recommended to use GC-MS and GC-ICP-MS systems, which provide good results with high sensitivity.

Table 3 Generic reference levels for different elements and countries.

Element	Andalusian (Spain) ¹			The Netherlands ²	USA ³		Italy ⁴	
	Industrial	Non industrial	Other uses		Industrial	Residential	Industrial	Residential
As	40	36	36	55	2	0,4	50	20
Cd	750	75	25	12	900	70	15	2
Co	250	25	24	240			250	20
Cu	10000	3130	595	190				
Total Cr	10000	10000	10000	380	3400	230	800	150
Cr(VI)	100	20	20				15	2
Hg	15	6	6	10	14	10	5	1
Ni	10000	1530	1530	210	23000	1600	500	120
Pb	2750	275	275	530	750	400	1000	100
Zinc	10000	10000	10000	720	340000	23000	1500	150

¹Decreto 18/2005; ²Denneman, C. (1999); ³US EPA (2001); ⁴Decreto Ministeriale 25 ottobre 1999